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Human Brain Project

Information Catalogue for EBRAINS CoCreate: Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-related Disorders

*Research and innovation roadmaps with long-term ambitions
and visions.*

Facilitated by EBRAINS Community Building Team

EBRAINS
Community

TEKNOLOGIRÅDET
DANISH BOARD OF TECHNOLOGY

Introducing EBRAINS

EBRAINS is a new digital research infrastructure, created by the EU-funded Human Brain Project, that gathers an extensive range of data and tools for brain related research. EBRAINS will capitalize on the work performed by the Human Brain Project teams in digital neuroscience, brain medicine, and brain-inspired technology, and will take it to the next level.

The EBRAINS ambition

EBRAINS draws on cutting-edge neuroscience, big data, computing, robotics, and related technologies to help translate the latest scientific discoveries into innovation in medicine and industry, for the benefit of patients and society. EBRAINS' ambition is to provide the scientific community at large with an open state-of-the-art capability that fosters collaborative brain science, opens the way to ground-breaking discoveries, and aims to secure Europe's leading position in the dynamically growing field of multidisciplinary brain research and its exploitation.

EBRAINS

Program

DAY 1: Wednesday June 7th 2023

WHEN	WHAT	WHERE
09:00 – 09:30	Breakfast	Bicycle, HUONE: Plenary
09:30 – 10:15	Welcome, introductions and Group formation	Bicycle, HUONE: Plenary
10:15 – 12:15	Identifying challenges and solutions part I	Bicycle, HUONE: Groups
12:15 – 13:15	Lunch	HUONE Restaurant area
13:15 – 13:30	Group formation	Bicycle, HUONE: Plenary
13:30 – 15:30	Identifying challenges and solutions part II	Bicycle, HUONE: Groups
15:30 – 16:00	Coffee/cake break	HUONE Restaurant area
16:00 – 16:30	Wrap-up and group formation day 2	Bicycle, HUONE: Plenary
18:30-21:30	Social Dinner	HUONE Restaurant area

DAY 2: Thursday June 8th 2023

WHEN	WHAT	WHERE
09:00 – 10:00	Breakfast and status	Bicycle, HUONE: Plenary
10:00 – 10:45	Initial roadmap formulation part I	Bicycle, HUONE: Groups
10:45 – 11:00	Break	HUONE Restaurant area
11:00 – 12:30	Initial roadmap formulation part II	Bicycle, HUONE: Groups
12:30 – 13:30	Lunch	HUONE Restaurant area
13:30 – 15:00	Creating a common coherent roadmap	Bicycle, HUONE: Plenary
15:00 – 15:15	Coffee/cake break	HUONE Restaurant area
15:15 – 16:15	Finalising roadmap	Bicycle, HUONE: Groups
16:15 – 16:30	Wrap up and see you online	Bicycle, HUONE: Plenary

Venue and accommodation

Workshop sessions on June 7th- 8th 2023.

Where to cocreate?

The venue is called HUONE and is placed on:

[Amager Strandvej 390](#)
[2770 Kastrup.](#)

Huone is located approximately 1 km from the Copenhagen Airport. It is a leading event centre that provides exceptional services to create great experiences for attendees. Our workshop will take place in The Bicycle Room which is inspired by the Danes' joy in cycling. The room is designed for dialogues and open debates making it the perfect setting for our workshop. Beside free access to coffee, HUONE will offer us a range of catering options, including morning- and lunch buffets and an afternoon break with cake, snacks, and healthier alternatives.

Where to stay?

We recommend you to book your stay at Best Western Plus Airport Hotel that has high standards and are located 400 m from the venue.

NOTE: You will get a favorable price when entering “attending a conference at HUONE” in the comment when booking.

Best Western Plus Airport Hotel Copenhagen, address:

[Kastruplundgade 15](#)
[2770 Kastrup](#)

Book [HERE](#)

How to get your expenses reimbursed?

The Human Brain Project will reimburse your travel- and accommodation expenses up to **650 EURO**. Please read the instructions [here](#) on how to fill out the formular which you will find [here](#).

Please send the filled-out reimbursement formular to asnb@tekno.dk no later than two weeks after the workshop.

Questions?

If you have any questions regarding the workshop sessions or your stay in Copenhagen, please do not hesitate to contact us! Write an email to asnb@tekno.dk with “CoCreate” in the subject heading.

Introduction

The **EBRAINS Community** is being built with and for the people developing, using, supporting, and benefiting from the EBRAINS Research Infrastructure, with an interdisciplinary and inclusive focus. In this context, the **EBRAINS CoCreate** process is a strategic community engagement process, which facilitates multi-actor collaboration on research and innovation roadmaps.

Research and innovation (R&I) agendas are generated at many different scales and levels, and by many different bodies, including the European Commission, governments, research agencies, funders, institutions, and individual researchers. A known tendency in this setup is that the scope is often limited by institutional thinking, disciplinary boundaries, or special interests. This leaves a need for defining research agendas across fields and actors, thereby defining more comprehensive and less biased priorities or directions for R&I programmes or projects.

EBRAINS CoCreate builds on the method of Open Research Agenda Setting (ORAS) which recognises the benefits of engaging multi-actors including civil society organisations, patient organisations and governance bodies in R&I development alongside scientific and technological experts. The resulting research agendas will in turn include visions or problems that societal actors find important, which strengthens and legitimises the selection of research priorities.

The **EBRAINS CoCreate Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-related Disorders** process is made up of four workshops arranged from May 2023 to June 2023 with the following set-up:

The **EBRAINS CoCreate Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-related Disorders** aims to:

- 1) Identify shared long-term ambitions within the areas of disorder identification and treatment.
- 2) Create roadmaps that allow the ambitions to evolve into tangible goals, tracks, and steps.
- 3) Identify opportunities to realise the R&I roadmaps.

Roadmap on Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-Related Disorders

EBRAINS CoCreate is a forward looking cocreation process that delivers roadmaps of visionary science and innovation targets that are important for EBRAINS as an infrastructure and for the multi-actor and interdisciplinary environment around it. The vision in a CoCreate is a societally beneficial one and, accordingly, the roadmap should lead towards positive impacts for society and the individual citizen. A roadmap splits the realisation of the vision up into a stepwise process and identifies needed collaborators and funding paths for at least the first steps.

EBRAINS CoCreate aims to address the issue of the availability of non-invasive screening methodologies towards brain-related disorders. Epidemiological correlations between various factors such as lifestyle, phenotypes, environmental exposure, and brain disorders can provide correlations as a starting point for new research on causality. Adding to this, access to more and improved non-invasive biomarkers such as genotypes and brain scanning methods may give promises of effective screenings. In combination, they give a promise of earlier and better detection, prediction and prognosis, and of increase in causality research.

The EBRIANS CoCreate workshop on Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-Related Disorders will work towards developing a roadmap that integrates the availability of non-invasive biomarkers with improved epidemiology. You will, as workshop participant, part take in creating a roadmap that researchers and innovators can use to develop new focused projects. The goal of this initiative is to improve the overall well-being of citizens by being better at early detection, diagnosis, prognosis, and prevention, and ultimately at treating and curing brain-related disorders.

An EBRAINS CoCreate has the clear aspiration to sketch an ambitious and promising roadmap and define which first steps can be realized by collaboration across disciplines and stakeholders. To this end, we want to gather a multidisciplinary group of stakeholders that collectively has insights into the relevant challenges and possibilities, as well as potential solutions and their realisation. Ideally, this means participation from experts and stakeholders in the fields of epidemiology, neuroscience, neurology, psychology, psychiatry, ethics, health data security, AI, and big data analysis, and patient organisations, health authorities, industry, and funding agencies.

Workshop session 1 – Brainstorming on sub-topics

The first workshop session was held online on May 17th. Here, we were enlightened by several of the participants who gave us interesting pitches about their perspective of the biggest advantage and/or challenge regarding epidemiology and non-invasive biomarkers to improve the understanding of brain-related disorders and how they wish to work with the overarching theme. Furthermore, a successful piece of work was cocreated by a brainstorming and elaboration phase in groups. The following tables provides an overview of the outcome of the group work from session 1.

Group 1

1.1 Data, big-data, data integration, data access, data structures, Data use

- Use of Ebrains KG and Labs to use and share datasets.
- AI and HPC to get pattern recognition and process data in compliance with GDPR.
- Multimodal neuroscience data integration (FAIR ontology/metadata). Combine structural, functional, metabolic, genetics data).
- Sharing and reusing results and data.
- Epidemiology driven study design.
- (representative disease relevant balance of age, sex etc in participants groups.)

Why:

- The most effective and widespread use of non-invasive technologies for early diagnosis, monitoring, and evaluation of the effectiveness of the treatment methods used.
- Data problem - data compatibility, repeatability of results, confirmation from different modalities.
- Complementarity of compatibility of (different) data.

Sketching the steps:

- Prospective FAIR data management plan with proactive curation harmonized within National nodes and internationally.
- Epidemiology driven study design.
- (representative disease relevant balance of age, sex etc. in participants groups).
- Multimodal neuroscience data integration (FAIR ontology/metadata).
- Combine structural, functional, metabolic, genetics etc. data).
- Multiscale brain models (based on multimodal data).
- Link epidemiology, multimodal data and multiscale models with clinical scores/behaviour.
- Infer multiscale biomarkers with data driven models.

1.2 Data generation, new data sources

- Using IOT to gather real time information.
- Probability and pattern recognition of external factors to support diagnostics.
- Infer multiscale biomarkers with data driven models.
- Multiscale brain models (based on multimodal data).

Why:

- Efficient use Infrastructure use and use of resources based on the scientific needs by assessment and standardization of the process by the use of templates and guides to evaluate requirements.
- Link epidemiology, multimodal data and multiscale models with clinical scores/behaviour.
- Epidemiology driven study design (representative disease relevant balance of age, sex etc in participants groups).
- Multimodal neuroscience data integration (FAIR ontology/metadata).
- Combine structural, functional, metabolic, genetics data).

Sketching the steps:

- Ebrains standardization and showcases to evaluate and inspire research.

1.3 early intervention, biomarkers, combining of biomarkers for early detection and expanded monitoring, cost (positive)

- Identify new biomarkers to improve the outcome of neurological diseases and lessen the socio-economic burden of these diseases.
- Early diagnosis/screening (autism, PTSD, depression, Parkinson, suicidal behavior, stroke).
- Individual monitoring of the current state (depression, Parkinson, stroke, age-related diseases) based on biomarkers different modalities.

- Practices unrelated to brain disease (mental health, public health, sport).

Why:

- The most effective and widespread use of non-invasive technologies for early diagnosis, monitoring, and evaluation of the effectiveness of the treatment methods used ← cheap, effective, wearable, non-clinical.

Group 2

2.1 Types of biomarkers, cognitive biomarkers, biomarkers for measuring environmental factors

- Cognitive and neurophysiological biomarkers.
- language model-based biomarkers using automatic speech recognition (ASR), machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI).
- The biomarker should be stable and reproducible, must reflect a function of a certain brain system and must be inherited.
- In epidemiological investigations, measurement of exposures by biomarkers is also another parameter.
- *“TEndophenotypes are heritable quantitative traits (such as EEG power in specific frequency bands or components of event-related potentials) that index an individual’s liability to develop or manifest a given disease or behavioral trait”* (Gottesman & Shields, 1972).

Sketching the steps:

- The role of environmental and biomarker measurements in explaining the exposure source to health outcome continuum. Environmental measurements from water, air, smoke, dust, and food are linked to biomarker measurements from blood, breath, and urine and are interpreted using different types of observational and mathematical tools, such as heat maps, bar graphs, and charts.
- 1. Define what non-invasive and epidemiological biomarkers are:
 - A **biomarker** is a measurable indicator of a biological state or condition. Biomarkers are critical to the rational development of medical therapeutics². A **non-invasive biomarker** is one that can be measured and evaluated without the need for invasive procedures such as tissue biopsy¹. An **epidemiological biomarker** is a biomarker used in epidemiological studies to enhance risk estimation and prediction of diseases⁴.
 - o References: (1) Biomarker definitions and their applications - PubMed. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29405771/>. (2) Biomarker measurement in non-invasively sampled colorectal ... - Nature. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41416-020-0893-8>. (3) BiomarkerCaRE: rationale and design of the European BiomarkerCaRE project <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25238720/>. (4) Liquid biopsy: an evolving paradigm for the biological ... - Nature. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41375-021-01339-6>. (5) HLA-A*03 - The Lancet. <https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanonc/article/PIIS1470-2045%2821%2900582-9/fulltext>.
 - 2. Map what existing frameworks exist:
 - There are several existing frameworks for non-invasive and epidemiological biomarkers. One such framework is the **liquid biopsy** approach which can offer powerful non-invasive biomarkers for diagnosis and monitoring treatment response of a variety of diseases¹. Another framework is the **biological approach** based on the quantification of biomarkers in serum samples and the **physical approach** based on the measurement of liver stiffness, using either ultrasound- or magnetic resonance-based elastography techniques².
 - o References: (1) Liquid Biopsy for Promising Non-invasive Diagnostic Biomarkers in <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11686-021-00444-x>. (2) Impact of non-invasive biomarkers on hepatology practice: Past, present <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168827822002008>. (3) A new approach to epigenome-wide discovery of non-invasive ... - PubMed. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/29686738/>.
 - 3. Based on the gathered information, suggest improvements and possible research for the combination of epidemiological and non-invasive biomarkers.
 - Why using functional brain diagnostics biomarkers:
 - o 1. Precise diagnostics and personalized therapy indications (e.g. for ADHD and ASD subtypes).
 - o 2. To construe protocol of individual treatment (personalized medicine).
 - o 3. To monitor drug effect.
 - o 4. To predict medication responses.
 - o 5. To support the development of new drugs.
 - The shift in paradigm - towards precision treatment in mental disorders. NIMH RDoC (Research Domain Criteria Initiative)
 - o ...*“transform diagnosis by incorporating genetics, imaging, cognitive science and other levels of information to lay the foundation for a new classification system.”*
 - Going beyond the subjective reports (narratives) and having diagnoses that incorporates nervous system and brain-related markers.
 - Existing non-invasive biomarkers: EEG, brief cognitive tests, questionnaires, saliva (?), retina scanning (?)
 - Future non-inv. biomarkers: ASR/AI-based speech and language models?
 - EEG (power spectra, arousal, vigilance, coherence, asymmetry) and ERPs (engagement component, inhibition component, self-monitoring and working memory components) biomarkers. Behavioral features from Go/NoGo tasks (omission, commission errors, RT, varRT).

2.2 Application of biomarkers in the population

- Biomarkers will encourage broader population research.
- General screening for dementia in the elderly population is not recommended due to the rate of false positives and the relatively poor treatment options.
- Monitor progression of disease in the individual to identify patterns of change in the population.

2.3 Benefits

- To detect and quantify abnormal brain organization and to identify subgroups of pathological abnormalities within groups of patients with similar symptoms
- Biomarkers also have the potential to identify neurological disease at an early stage, to provide a method for homogeneous classification of a disease, and to extend our knowledge-base concerning the underlying disease pathogenesis.
- non invasive bio markers are less expensive than invasive so larger groups of participants

Sketching the steps:

- Combining epidemiological and non-invasive biomarker research can help in the early detection of diseases such as breast cancer and Alzheimer's disease. For example, circulating carcinoma antigens, circulating tumor cells, circulating cell-free tumor nucleic acids (DNA or RNA), circulating microRNAs, and circulating extracellular vesicles in the peripheral blood, nipple aspirate fluid, sweat, urine, and tears, as well as volatile organic compounds in the breath have emerged as potential non-invasive biomarkers for early detection of breast cancer¹. Similarly, new fluid biomarkers tracking non-amyloid- β and non-tau pathology in Alzheimer's disease have shown promise².

- References: (1) Non-Invasive Biomarkers for Early Detection of Breast Cancer. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32992445/>. (2) New fluid biomarkers tracking non-amyloid- β and non-tau ... - Nature. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s12276-020-0418-9>. (3) Full article: A first-in-class, non-invasive, immunodynamic biomarker <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/2162402X.2021.2024692>.

Group 3

3.1 Data collection and security

- Longitudinal and latitudinal (cross-sectional) studies can be done, i.e., follow the progress in each patient (changes over time) but also extract the common features of populations (behavior and scores) - convergence with dynamical system approach of diseases evolution (Eiko).
- Multiple data use / transferrable and universal data.
- Decentralised data collection and precise analytical processes which takes into account philosophical invasiveness there can be privacy, consent and also tracking of exact resonance in functioning. further it prevents generalisation and vague labelling, which also adds to issues of misdiagnosis or u relatability.
- Thinking of blockchain technology or a model like that for data.

Sketching the steps:

- DEVELOP DEVICES! Invest money and efforts to create reliable daily usable devices to track biomarkers (not only focusing on expensive and inaccessible devices as fMRI, MEG...).
- COLLECT DATA! Increase the investment in longitudinal research and keep or increase the investment in cross-sectional studies.
- MODEL! Use models to bridge between the data and the neural activity (this is usually a hard link because what we measure is in macroscopic level relates to the microscopic level in a complex manner).
- DATA ANALYSIS: Compare different sets of data (containing information from multiple diseases) to better understand the underlying mechanisms and boundaries.
- DISEASE CLASSIFICATION: Refine the classification of the diseases, maybe considering more the symptoms.
- APPLICATIONS: Since we have well-defined borderings and data, we can think about several applications from developing biofeedback devices to monitor (track) the evolution of a disease, predict crises and there on.

3.2 Disease management

- Early detection and diagnosis.
- Preventive measures.
- Foresee and monitor relapses.
- Prediction of prognosis.
- Prevent or alert about a crisis based on the signals.

Sketching the steps:

- Define visions.
- In terms of education - bridging science and humanities and funneling it through art and technology.
- Neha: at policy level it translates into something as simple as basic income, free healthcare, infrastructural support, (sensorial indexes -noise/light/ nature - that take into account the triggers and disease experienced) [at the heart of it is inclusivity and respect and making space for life in whatever form it exists].
- 1) design devices (as jewelry) 2) use naturally occurring bio responsive organisms as part of the materials (lichens/algae) 3) collect data of individuals in different states and train AI data models to identify what is their optimal state 4) identify triggers and response sets to build optimal data environments which can be used for neurofeedback based on the data of the individuals themselves.
 - Neha: this is probably what would fall in the category IOT?
 - Neha: still not too clear as to how lichens can be integrated - but there is an element of symbiosis as well as naturally occurring and tangible signs responding to shifts in environments (bioluminescence for example - I don't know if it is experienced as 'instability or pain' in that world/species - but there is a possible cross species-kingdom collaboration calling in from that place -- just to elaborate a little on that inquiry - this has emerged from an experiment in working with discarded materials (mostly those invested with emotional value) in the context of relationship with environment (esp. the river) and breakdown of community structures during the pandemic - the form and knots of the fabric took the shape of the coronavirus and mutated further - it is still a partially formulated correlation/ hypothesis - since there aren't clearly validated data points and tangible scientifically approved proof to make that connection ---- however it might be an interesting direction to pursue, even if not a terribly accurate piece - especially given the rise in flaring up and surfacing of chronic conditions like ME/cfs and FMS in cases of long covid.
- Investment can come in products (accessories/apparel/ home decor/ artwork) which can be bio responsive and/or environments (gaming/ events/ experiences) that bring together people in neuronal resonance and give biofeedback.
- Design low-cost experiments and prototypes based on available resources and then expand/scale it through funding?
- Neha: a part of disease management also comes from an understanding what is 'normal' or state of ease- which is extremely context and conditioning driven - also the blurring lines between discomfort and expansion, at species and consciousness level?
- Neha: what is a 'healthy' brain? criteria of mind/ body - is there an [empty] space or block of knowledge where there are undefined conditions of the brains - as in - here is a symptom - an observation/excavation/finding which does not have a positive or negative connotation to it (even if it is apparently uneasy/debilitating or exhilarating for that matter) - but just a phenomenon to be investigated? e.g.: what is my body learning to do/ respond or adapt to as it displays symptoms of bipolarity or chronic fatigue or pain - and how can that learning itself be supported in the way my organism is tending organically? what is making itself appear or trying to take shape through these kind of resistors(resistance) of being/embodying? what kind of learnings do we have encoded in deformities/disabilities/disorders and diversities? (Going back to curiosity and play) [at what point does treatment- as an idea- become invasive]? Are there existing intersecting fields and/or methodologies between consciousness studies and brain research?
- Neha: what role does/can data of altered states (meditation/ trial practices/ psychedelics/engrossment in art or any high concentration practice) play in management of disease- through biofeedback - for instance do we/can we determine one's personal healthy state parameters/ reference from data points accessed from 'altered/ non-ordinary states'?

3.3 Disease narrative

- Understand "healthy" physiology.
- We can move away from breaking down into symptomatic labelling to resonance in neuronal activity modelling.
- Help doing better labeling in mental illness.
- Objectification of disease and thereby reducing stigma.
- Need to move from "disease" to "ease", both infrastructurally and in terms of narrative. to be able to see "disorders" as difference in perception, an encoded evolutionary adaptation -- which is not stigmatised or forced to be managed to fixed to fit into a normative, functional management approach.

Sketching the steps

- International convention of data security, storage, and access.
- Create a blockchain based data system.
- Neha: decentralising data can be crucial in terms of addressing that philosophical implication of 'invasiveness' - also allow for more precise diagnostics and not centralised and generalised approaches - especially in the time of such massive information and data availability.

- Steps for narrative - curiosity and play, linguistics and language structures.
- Design an experiment with individuals who can also collaborate as a group.
- To move to the vocabulary of Brain - neuronal activity / diverse perception symptoms - if we wish to destigmatize it then our starting point has to be free from that bias of looking at what we observe as "disorder". Disease and disorders are measured based on what is considered normal and functional in a certain ethical and economic framework. We cannot look at the possibilities offered through our perception and brains if we aren't able to contextualise, historicise in consciously and strategically naming modes of perception.
- Neha: it is a fine line in this narrative because one needs to be able acknowledge a problem/disease for what it does - to impede one's growth and at the same time understanding how to transmute it into something which becomes a space of 'ease' - also humanities, studies of culture, language, art have a crucial role to play in this aspect, in terms of cognition (as linguistic frameworks) as well as the formation of perceptive imaginary/ collective resonance - affirmation of reality and structure of feeling.

Group 4

4.1 Data structures, Data security

- Data Security.
- Bias - Scaling individual to large population.

4.2 Behavioural biomarkers, ethical boundaries

- In relation to addressing the behavioural component, the concerns are bias, and meaningfulness/relevance of statistical analyses of large datasets. In particular, we can drill down different types of behaviour (a taxonomy of behaviour? for example, physiological, cognitive, social, etc). There are great ETHICAL implications when using BEHAVIOUR as categoris (to what extent is it ethical to standarzied behaviour).
- Diseases with a behavioural component.

4.3 Combination of biomarkers and epidemiology, early diagnosis

- Marta: Use epidemiological data to identify neurobiological and behavioural rhythms (circadian,circalunar, circaannual, seasonal ..) that may help to better understand brain-related disorders.
- Marta: Harnessing epidemiological data to investigate non-invasive biomarkers related with brain health.
- Marta: From epidemiological data on brain disorders, risk factors can be derived. These risk factors could be divided into: modifiable/non-modifiable and by typology (e.g. environmental, behavioural, physiologic ...). Brain disorder - risk factor pairs can be identified, and this causal relationship (supported by epidemiological studies) can be studied from a neurobiological point of view. As a result of this study, we could identify non-invasive biomarkers in several domains: genes, molecules, circuits, physiology, behaviour, environment. Validate these biomarkers in longitudinal studies populations or large populations (at this point gold-standard measures are needed). Tools of epidemiology could be used. Markers of risk exposure could also be investigated.

Six suggested sub-topics

As the above tables show, the work cocreated by the participants do in some cases overlap or intertwine. Therefore, we have created six suggestions for sub-topics to work further on, based on the cocreated outcome of session 1 – the numbers after each point refer to group and cluster in the tables above. The suggested sub-topics are not set in stone and will be co-developed, elaborated on, and/or modified during the workshop sessions in Copenhagen. However, they will be the starting point for the discussions when we meet for the next sessions.

Review and gap analysis of epidemiology and screening

Finding the blank spots on the epidemiological map. What is state of the art in the epidemiology of brain health? What are areas that could or should be explored as consequence of having access to new data sources and biomarkers? Is existing data being used well-enough in the epidemiology of brain health? What can be learned from other areas of epidemiology?

- 1.1 Data, big-data, data integration, data access, data structures, Data use
- 2.3 Benefits
- 3.3 Disease narrative
- 4.3 Combination of biomarkers and epidemiology, early diagnosis

New data sources and biomarker opportunities

New technological advances can give access to new biomarkers, which provide new types of data. Patient records have become more comprehensive, accessible, and easier to analyse. How should structures be built to take advantage of this?

- 1.2 Data generation, new data sources
- 2.1 Types of biomarkers, cognitive biomarkers, biomarkers for measuring environmental factors
- 3.1 Data collection and security

Solving ethical issues in new biomarkers and epidemiology

Big data sets and new types of biomarkers provide new ethical challenges. How do we understand disease? What does it mean for a biomarker to be non-invasive?... How can the needed ethical safeguards be developed and implemented?

- 3.1 Data collection and security
 - 3.3 Disease narrative
- 4.1 Data structures, Data security
- 4.2 Behavioural biomarkers, ethical boundaries

Integrating biomarkers and epidemiology

The epidemiological perspective: How should new biomarkers and epidemiological research be combined to best take advantage of the potential synergy? What novel insights can be produced by this integration, and how?

- 1.1 Data, big-data, data integration, data access, data structures, Data use
- 2.1 Types of biomarkers, cognitive biomarkers, biomarkers for measuring environmental factors
- 2.2 Application of biomarkers in the population
- 3.1 Data collection and security
- 4.3 Combination of biomarkers and epidemiology, early diagnosis

Biomarker big data for early detection

The screening perspective: New biomarkers, expanded access to data, and improved epidemiology enable better screening for individuals. What types of biomarkers, data, and collaborations are needed to enable early detection of brain related diseases?

- 1.1 Data, big-data, data integration, data access, data structures, Data use
- 1.3 early intervention, biomarkers, combining of biomarkers for early detection and expanded monitoring, cost (positive)
- 2.2 Application of biomarkers in the population
- 2.3 Benefits
- 3.2 Disease management
- 4.3 Combination of biomarkers and epidemiology, early diagnosis

Pathways to practical outcomes of epidemiology

Better epidemiology and new biomarkers produce new insights and knowledge. Next steps could be to investigate causality, initiate programs for prevention, new policies for brain health, etc. How to ensure that these findings have broad and deep impact?

- 1.1 Data, big-data, data integration, data access, data structures, Data use
- 1.2 Data generation, new data sources
 - 2.3 Benefits
- 3.2 Disease management
- 3.3 Disease narrative

EBRAINS Community

This CoCreation event on Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-Related Disorders is organized by the EBRAINS Community Building Team. EBRAINS Community is a growing online community within neuroscience, brain medicine, and brain-related technology. Whether you are looking for other EBRAINS users, would like to engage in research facilitated by the EBRAINS services and tools, or find elements of neuroscience and brain-related technology interesting, the odds are you will find like-minded in the EBRAINS Community.

Sign up for EBRAINS Community

Follow the link below and you will be sent directly to the first destination of your journey, the sign-up page. Simply sign-up with your EBRAINS Account or with your e-mail and click 'Sign up as Member'. The next step is then to verify your e-mail address through an e-mail that will be sent directly to your e-mail inbox. Give it a few minutes and remember to check your spam folder!

When you have signed up as a member and logged in, it is time for you to start building your personal profile. You simply follow the steps that you will be presented when you access your profile:

1. First name
2. Surname
3. Choose a minimum of one field of interest

Now press '**Publish to EBRAINS**' and start using the features and functions! You can always access your profile at a later time to fill in additional information or edit your profile.

Join our *open* sub-community '**EBRAINS CoCreate & Unconference**' to connect and chat with fellow participants and be the first to receive information about our events!

Join the EBRAINS community here:

community.ebrains.eu

List of participants

Anastasiia	Andriievska	RISE Research Institutes, Sweden
Carolina	Ciomas	CHUV, Switzerland
Chitaranjan	Mahapatra	CNRS/Paris-Saclay Institute of Neuroscience, France
George	Ogoh	DMU, United Kingdom
Igori	Comarovschii	Karolinska Institute, Sweden
João Miguel	Alves Ferreira	University of Coimbra Faculty of Medicine, Portugal
Jose Cruz	Sanchez Ramirez	UNAM, Germany
Judith	D Clarke	Hebb's Hub, United Kingdom
Kasper	Jørgensen	Danish Dementia Research Centre at Rigshospitalet, Denmark
Lavinia Mitiko	Takarabe	Universite Aix-Marseille, France
Magdalene	Chan	British Neuroscience Association, United Kingdom
Manuel	Menendez Gonzalez	Fundacion de Neurociencias, Spain
Marissa	Diaz	Jülich Supercomputing Centre, Germany
Marta	Alvarez	Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, Spain
Mohamedi	Darghal	Neuropsychopharmacology, Morocco
Monica	Tarcea	UMFST, Romania
Neha	Chaturvedi	UP80 Space for Transdisciplinary Collaborative Practices, India
Paola	Di Maio	CSKRNS, United Kingdom
Samara	Chrysoula	International Hellenic University, Greece
Serhii	Tukaiev	Università della Svizzera Italiana, Switzerland
Silvana	Markovska-Simoska	Macedonian Academy of Sciences and Arts, North Macedonia
Tanja	Hasse	University of Zurich, Switzerland
Tejaswi	Meshram	Pifi, India
Veronika	Stoka	J. Stefan Institute, Slovenia

Human Brain Project

Behind EBRAINS CoCreate

EBRAINS CoCreate on Epidemiology and Non-Invasive Biomarkers to Improve the Understanding of Brain-Related Disorders is run by The Danish Board of Technology, a part of the Human Brain Project and EBRAINS Community Building Team

Facilitated and created by:

Lars Klüver

Augusta Bennedbæk

Rasmus Mikkelsen

community@ebrains.eu

www.humanbrainproject.eu

<https://ebrains.eu/>

<https://community.ebrains.eu/login>

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